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Who should the government listen to? Science or Opinions?

Evidence of the perceived politicization of science

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Abstract

The politicization of science, especially in government decision-making, has profound implications for public trust and policy acceptance. This study examines how people view the role of science in governmental decisions, comparing preferences for scientific evidence versus opinion polls across factual versus value-based and controversial versus non-controversial domains. Consistent with our hypotheses, participants viewed factual decisions as more suitable for scientific input than value-based ones, but controversial issues were less likely to be perceived as requiring scientific evidence, particularly in factual domains. Additionally, factors such as political orientation, populist beliefs, and psychological distance from science influenced these perceptions. This nuanced view of science's role in policy highlights the impact of public opinion on perceived scientific authority and underscores the challenges in maintaining science as a neutral policy informant.

Introduction

Understanding whether science is perceived to be politicized is crucial in the current state of our society where people hesitate about whether to trust COVID vaccines due to who endorses them (Abbas, 2022), or where a major science magazine endorses a democrat political candidate (Editors, 2024; Rubin, 2024) or a prestigious scientific journal rejects a far-right president (Editorial, 2022).

Perception of politicized science can shape public opinion, and have concrete effects at the individual and collective levels: For instance, individuals who are presented with a scientific article from a journal or lab that is associated with an opposite political spectrum see it as less credible than if associated to the same spectrum (Johnson et al., 2024; Robertson, 2021).

Perceived politicization of a certain issue or domain undermines the role of science as a common ground across parties in politics (Bolsen & Druckman, 2018), they can influence (de)funding decisions towards science, or explain active as well as passive resistance towards science education or science recommendations (Schmid-Petri et al., 2022).

This project aimed to find an approach that can help measure whether science is politicized and what moderates it by focusing on people's beliefs about what should inform governmental decisions across different domains. Political decisions can be based on opinions or scientific evidence. In principle, decisions regarding coordinating or aggregating values would be based on opinions, while decisions regarding factual domains would be based on scientific evidence.

Here, we are interested in testing whether people's judgments concur with this principle. We asked people to determine, for a series of future-looking decisions concerning either value or factual domains, controversial or not, how much the government should consult two sources of information: opinion polls or scientific evidence.

The distinction between value and factual, controversial and non-controversial, domains was validated based on a pilot study with independent raters (see Methods) who determined whether a list of decisions were matters of subjective values or objective facts, as well as whether the decisions would be politically controversial and what importance they had for society.

Then, our pre-registered predictions (Niella et al., 2024) were as follows:

1. Decisions that concern factual domains will overall be perceived as requiring significantly more scientific evidence than opinion polls compared with decisions that concern value domains.
2. In terms of the controversial domain of the decisions, we propose the following competing hypotheses:
 - a. Controversial decisions (as opposed to non-controversial) will be perceived as requiring more scientific evidence than opinion polls
 - b. Controversial decisions (as opposed to non-controversial) will be perceived as requiring less scientific evidence than opinion polls
 - c. Controversial decisions (as opposed to non-controversial) won't be perceived as requiring more scientific evidence than opinion polls, nor the other way around
3. There will be a significant interaction between the controversial/non-controversial and factual/value domains of the decisions on the perception of how much scientific evidence vs opinion polls should be required
4. The effects in hypotheses 1. and 2. will be moderated by:
 - a. Endorsement of populist beliefs (Uysal et al., 2024),
 - b. political ideology,
 - c. political orientation,
 - d. psychological distance to science (Većkalov et al., 2024)

Results

Hypotheses 1 & 2

Firstly, we want to check that decisions involving factual domains will be perceived as requiring significantly more scientific evidence than opinion polls compared with decisions involving value domains. And secondly, we wanted to test whether the controversial aspect of the decision presented any differences as well.

To do this, we first fitted a mixed-effects linear regression model with ‘SE Listen’ (how much the government should listen to scientific evidence as opposed to opinion polls on a scale from 0 to 10) as the dependent variable and Factual and Controversial as predictors and accounting for Participant IDs as random intercepts and slopes¹.

This shows that the effect of factual is statistically significant and positive ($B = 4.72$, 95% CI[4.62, 4.82], $t(23438) = 96.02$, $p < .001$; Std. B = 0.70, 95% CI[0.68, 0.71]) confirming our first hypothesis. Moreover, the effect of Controversial is statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.07$, 95% CI[-0.13, -5.80e-03], $t(23438) = -2.14$, $p = 0.032$; Std. B = -0.01, 95% CI [-0.02, -8.58e-04]), this confirms our second hypothesis, in particular, Hypothesis 2.b, predicting that the controversial decisions will be perceived as requiring less scientific evidence than the non-controversial ones. See Table 1 for details.

Hypothesis 3

Our next hypothesis aimed to test whether a decision's controversial aspect interacts with the differences in SE Listen between the factual and value aspects of the decisions. For this, we ran a linear mixed model with the interaction between Factual and Controversial as predictors and accounting for Participant ID as random intercepts and slopes.

This showed that the effect of this interaction is statistically significant and negative ($\beta = -1.21$, 95% CI[-1.32, -1.10], $t(23437) = -21.76$, $p < .001$; Std. $\beta = -0.09$, 95% CI [-0.10, -0.08]). See Table 1. This confirms our third hypothesis predicting that the controversial

¹ We originally pre-registered our models to use topic as random intercepts rather than participant id as random slopes. However, this was a mistake given that the topics of the decisions are not random, they were validated and selected as each belonging to one of the 4 categories which represent the 2 main predictor in the model (see Sup. info). Moreover, it is crucial to account for the variability between participants, since each participant responded to all 24 statements.

aspect of a decision will affect the perceived requirement of scientific evidence for a decision between Factual and Value-based decisions. This is portrayed in Figure 1, where we see that in the Factual domain, Controversial decisions are perceived as requiring less scientific evidence than Noncontroversial ones, and the other way around for the decisions in the Value domain.

	Model 1	Model 2
Factual	4.72 *** [4.62, 4.82]	5.33 *** [5.22, 5.44]
Controversial	-0.07 * [-0.13, -0.01]	0.54 *** [0.45, 0.62]
Factual*Controversial		-1.21 *** [-1.32, -1.10]
N	23448	23448
N (prolific_id)	977	977
AIC	105509.57	105047.56
BIC	105590.19	105136.25
R2 (fixed)	0.49	0.49
R2 (total)	0.59	0.60

Standard errors are heteroskedasticity robust. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Table 1. Summary of linear mixed effects models where 1. predicts SE listen with Factual (1 if factual, 0 if value) and Controversial (1 if controversial, 0 if noncontroversial), 2. adds the interaction between Factual and Controversial. The models accounted for Participant ID (prolific_id) as random slopes and intercepts.

Figure 1. Violin plot of SE listen (0 - 10 sliding scale from ‘listen to Opinion polls only’ to ‘Scientific Evidence only’) averaged across topics (Factual: alpha = .7, Factual Controversial: alpha = .7, Value: alpha= .7, Value Controversial: Alpha = .75) by Category and Controversial aspect, portraying significance scores for Wilcoxon tests between groups.

Hypothesis 4

Finally, we predicted that other individual aspects may moderate the effects of Factual and Controversial on SE Listen respectively.

Political Orientation

To start we tested this for political orientation, ‘Political Right’ (5-point scale, from ‘Very left’ to ‘Very right’). We ran a linear mixed-effects model including the following interactions as predictors: Controversial and Political Right, and Factual and Political Right. The model accounted for Participant ID as random intercepts and slopes.

In this model the interaction between Factual and Political Right is statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.10$, 95% CI [-0.20, -2.06e-03], $t(22547) = -2.00$, $p < 0.05$; Std.B= -0.01, 95% CI [-0.03, -2.94e-04]); and the interaction between Controversial and Political Right is statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.18$, 95% CI [-0.25, -0.11], $t(22547) = -5.29$, $p < .001$; Std.B= -0.03, 95% CI [-0.03, -0.02]). See Table 2 for more details on the model.

Political Ideology

Next we ran the same model but with our political ideology measure, ‘Political Conservative’ (5-point scale, from ‘Very liberal’ to ‘Very conservative’). Similarly, the interaction between Controversial and Political Conservative is statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.18$, 95% CI [-0.24, -0.11], $t(22283) = -5.23$, $p < .001$; Std. B = -0.03, 95% CI [-0.03, -0.02]). Nevertheless, the interaction between Factual and Political Conservative is negative but not statistically significant ($B = -0.09$, 95% CI [-0.19, 0.01], $t(22283) = -1.75$, $p = 0.081$; Std. B = -0.01, 95% CI [-0.03, 1.55e-03]). See Table 2 for more details.

These results suggest that the effects of both the factual and controversial domains are significantly moderated by people’s political orientation and only the controversial domain by ideology. In Figure 2, it can be seen that in Factual Decisions, controversial ones are perceived as requiring less scientific evidence than non-controversial ones and this difference grows as the Political Orientation goes up to ‘Very Right’. And for Value decisions, controversial decisions are perceived as requiring more scientific evidence than non-controversial ones and this difference becomes smaller as the Political Orientation goes up to ‘Very Right’.

How much should the government listen to Scientific Evidence?
 Answers about government decisions by respondents' political orientation

Figure 2. The figure displays the relationship between political orientation and respondents' views on how much the government should consider scientific evidence (SE Listen), with data points binned by political orientation and shown separately for factual and value-based question categories. On the x-axis, political orientation ranges on a 5-point scale from "Very Left" to "Very Right." The y-axis represents SE Listen. Points represent mean responses within each bin, colored by Controversial domain—"Controversial" or "Non-controversial". Loess smooth lines indicate trends with 95% confidence intervals.

	H4: Pol. Orientation	H4: Pol. Ideology
Factual	5.02 *** [4.72, 5.31]	4.99 *** [4.71, 5.28]
Controversial	0.42 *** [0.23, 0.61]	0.41 *** [0.22, 0.60]
Political Right	-0.12 * [-0.21, -0.03]	
Political Conservative		-0.14 ** [-0.23, -0.05]
Factual*PolRight	-0.10 * [-0.20, -0.00]	
Controversial*PolRight	-0.18 *** [-0.25, -0.11]	
Factual*PolConserv.		-0.09 [-0.19, 0.01]
Controversial*PolConserv.		-0.18 *** [-0.24, -0.11]
N	22560	22296
N (prolific_id)	940	929
AIC	101184.16	99938.89
BIC	101288.47	100043.05
R2 (fixed)	0.50	0.50
R2 (total)	0.60	0.60

Standard errors are heteroskedasticity robust. *** p < 0.001; ** p < 0.01; * p < 0.05.

Table 2. Summary of results for linear mixed method models with 1. Political Orientation and 2. Political Ideology as moderator for Factual and for Controversial respectively. The model accounted for Participant ID as random slopes and intercepts.

Psychological Distance to Science (PSYDISC)

Next, we tested whether participants' level of Psychological distance to science (PSYDISC) moderates the effects of Factual and Controversial in how much Scientific Evidence is perceived to be necessary for making government decisions. Again, we ran a mixed effects linear model with PSYDISC ($\alpha = .86$) as predictor and moderator of Factual and Controversial respectively. The interaction between PSYDISC and Factual is statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.37$, 95% CI[-0.52, -0.21], $t(23435) = -4.72$, $p < .001$; Std. beta = -0.03, 95% CI [-0.05, -0.02]). The interaction between Controversial and PSYDISC is

statistically significant and negative ($B = -0.19$, 95% CI $[-0.29, -0.09]$, $t(23435) = -3.67$, $p < .001$; Std. B $= -0.02$, 95% CI $[-0.03, -8.14e-03]$). See Table 3 for more details.

In Figure 3 we see that overall, in Factual decisions, the higher the PSYDISC, the less Scientific Evidence is perceived to be needed for the governmental decisions. For Factual decisions, controversial ones are perceived as requiring less Scientific evidence than non-controversial ones and this difference stays consistent as PSYDISC goes up. For Value decisions, however, the opposite difference exists (controversial decisions require more scientific evidence than noncontroversial ones) although it disappears as PSYDISC goes up.

Figure 3. This figure shows the relationship between respondents' psychological distance to science (PSYDISC) and their support for the government considering scientific evidence in decision-making (SE Listen). Linear trend lines are plotted for "Controversial" and "Non-controversial" domains. The data is faceted by decision category (factual or value-based).

H4: Psychological Distance to Science

Factual	5.67 *** [5.27, 6.08]
Controversial	0.42 ** [0.15, 0.69]
PSYDISC	-0.22 ** [-0.35, -0.08]
Factual*PSYDISC	-0.37 *** [-0.52, -0.21]
Controversial*PSYDISC	-0.19 *** [-0.29, -0.09]
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N	23448
N (prolific_id)	977
AIC	105368.44
BIC	105473.25
R2 (fixed)	0.50
R2 (total)	0.59

Standard errors are heteroskedasticity robust. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Summary of results for linear mixed method model with Psychological Distance to Science (PSYDISC) as moderator for Factual and for Controversial respectively. The model accounted for Participant ID as random slopes and intercepts.

Populist Beliefs

To test whether our measure of Populist Beliefs ('Populist') moderated the effects of Factual and Controversial on SE listen we ran the same linear mixed model with Populist (alpha = 0.8) as moderator this time. Here, the interaction between Factual and Populist is statistically significant and positive (beta = 0.12, 95% CI [7.63e-04, 0.25], $t(23435) = 1.97$, $p < .05$; Std. beta = 0.01, 95% CI [8.81e-05, 0.03]) meaning that the higher populist beliefs people hold, the strongest the difference between factual and Value domains decisions become (factual decisions are perceived as requiring more scientific evidence than value ones). The interaction between controversial and populist is statistically significant and negative (B = -0.09, 95%CI [-0.17,-0.01], $t(23435) = -2.21$, $p < .05$; Std. B = -0.01, 95%CI [-0.02, -1.19e-03], meaning that the higher populist beliefs people hold, the weakest the difference between controversial and noncontroversial decisions becomes. See Table 4 for more details.

Similar to PSYDISC, in Figure 4 we see that in factual decisions noncontroversial ones are perceived as requiring more scientific evidence than controversial ones and this difference is consistent as Populist goes up; whereas for value decisions the difference is reverse and it disappears as Populist goes up.

H4: Populist Beliefs

Factual	4.28 *** [3.83, 4.73]
Controversial	0.26 [-0.04, 0.55]
Populist	-0.40 *** [-0.50, -0.29]
Factual*Populist	0.12 * [0.00, 0.25]
Controversial*Populist	-0.09 * [-0.17, -0.01]

N	23448
N (prolific_id)	977
AIC	105431.89
BIC	105536.71
R2 (fixed)	0.49
R2 (total)	0.59

Standard errors are heteroskedasticity robust. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. Summary of results for linear mixed method model with Populist Beliefs (Populist) as moderator for Factual and for Controversial respectively. The model accounted for Participant ID as random slopes and intercepts.

How much should the government listen to Scientific Evidence?
Answers about government decisions by respondents' Pop. Beliefs level

Figure 4. This figure shows the relationship between respondents' Populist Beliefs (Populist) and their support for the government considering scientific evidence in decision-making (SE Listen). Linear trend lines are plotted for "Controversial" and "Non-controversial" domains. The data is faceted by decision category (factual or value-based).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides evidence that public perception of whether science or opinion polls should guide governmental decisions is significantly influenced by the nature of the issue—whether factual or value-based—and its controversial status. Specifically, factual domains are generally seen as requiring more scientific evidence than value-based ones, though this need is perceived to decrease when the issue is controversial. Additionally, individual factors, such as political orientation, psychological distance to science, and endorsement of populist beliefs, moderate these perceptions. For instance, respondents with higher psychological distance to science showed a diminishing preference for scientific evidence in factual issues. These findings reveal nuanced ways in which political, psychological, and ideological factors impact public attitudes toward the role of science in governance, highlighting potential barriers to achieving science-informed policy in polarized environments.

Methods

Sample

Using Prolific, we surveyed 1000 UK participants ($n= 977$ after removing those who failed attention checks or respondents with equal IP addresses). Our study had ethics approval from the Ethics Commission in the Philosophy Department at Ludwig Maximilians Universität Munich. Our sample was 51.28% Female, 48.21% Male, and 0.51% Non-binary participants, the mean age was 46.81 ($SD = 15.97$), and their political identities were measured in two ways: Political Orientation (5 point Likert-scale: very left, left, center, right, very right) and Political Ideology (5 point Likert-scale: very liberal, liberal, moderate, conservative, very very conservative), the distribution of responses for these two measure can be seen below:

Survey

The survey had three main sections: Main Task, Other Scales, and Demographics. Each section included Attention Checks.

- Main Task:

Participants were presented with a total of 24 Government Decisions, each one belonging to one of four categories: Value Controversial, Value Noncontroversial, Factual Controversial, and Factual Noncontroversial (six per category). These decision statements were previously validated (see section below). The order in which the decisions were presented was randomized between participants.

For each government decision (e.g., ‘the government needs to decide whether to change the fees on public transport to encourage more people to use it’), participants were asked to respond: “*Who should the government listen to when making this decision?*”

To answer, participants used a slider from "Opinion Polls only" (the government should only base its decision on Opinion Polls) to "Scientific Evidence Only" (the government should only base its decision on Scientific Evidence) that looked like this:

Half of the participants had Opinion Polls on the left and Scientific Evidence on the right, and the other half had it the other way around. When analyzing data those with Opinion Polls on the right were recoded to match with responses that had Scientific Evidence on the right. On the experimenter side, the scale was continuous with 2 decimals and went from 0 (on the left) to 10 (on the right), which is how the responses were recorded - participants just had to position the cursor but did not see the values.

After all 24 decisions were presented, participants were presented with the following open-text question for future analyses: *“Please use the box below to describe, in your own words, your general thought process when choosing between Opinion Polls and Scientific Evidence throughout the different government decisions.”*

- Government Decisions:

The 24 government decisions were selected from a list of 97 statements created by the authors and checked by other colleagues and graduate students equal amount of statements belonging to one of the following 4 categories: 1. **Value-based, non-controversial** (e.g., changing hospital chair colors), 2. **Value-based, controversial** (e.g., altering religious holidays), 3. **Factual, non-controversial** (e.g., approving a new migraine treatment), 4. **Factual, controversial** (e.g., updating the minimum age for mandatory COVID vaccination). To select 6 per category, we ran a validation survey with over 700 raters (around 100 responses per statement) where participants categorized each statement into 3 dimensions:

1. Does this decision mostly depend on ..? facts/opinions/not sure
2. Is this decision politically charged? Yes/No/not sure

3. How much impact do you think this issue may have in society?

insignificant/moderate/significant.

The top 6 decisions per category were then selected based on the scores they received accordingly. For instance, for ‘factual’, the proportion of ‘facts’ in 1 that each decision received; for ‘controversial’ the proportion of ‘yes’ in 2 that each decision received, and controlling for impact in society by filtering out decisions that were on the extremes. The selected decisions per category were:

Category	Decisions
Factual Controversial	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The government needs to decide whether to create new rules on renewable energy in public buildings to reduce environmental impact. 2. The government needs to decide whether to change regulations on deep-sea mining and exploration to reflect the risks to biodiversity 3. The government needs to decide whether to adjust the recommended age group for COVID-19 vaccine boosters to safeguard public health 4. The government needs to decide whether to revise coastal protection regulations to limit ocean acidification 5. The government needs to decide whether to revise regulations on GMOs (genetically modified organisms) used in agriculture to improve food safety 6. The government needs to decide whether to update the educational curriculum to include recent findings on colonial history and its impacts
Factual Non Controversial	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The government needs to decide whether to revise food safety regulations for restaurants to make sure dairy products do not contain salmonella bacteria 2. The government needs to decide whether to revise building standards based on seismic research to guarantee safety 3. The government needs to decide whether to update the rules for password encryption in software to improve security 4. The government needs to decide whether to legalize new migraine treatments to provide more personalized care. 5. The government needs to decide whether to change regulations on a new pain-relief medication to be authorized for children under the age of 6 6. The government needs to decide whether to change the number of reflective posts on roads to improve safety.
Value Controversial	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The government needs to decide whether to change the rules authorizing public demonstrations to restrict possibly offensive content 2. The government needs to decide whether to change dress codes in public schools to avoid religious signaling 3. The government needs to decide whether to update bans on specific books in public libraries or schools to adjust to inappropriate or offensive contents 4. The government needs to decide whether to add minority languages to the official languages of the country 5. The government needs to decide whether to adjust public holiday schedules

	<p>to better align with significant cultural or historical events</p> <p>6. The government needs to decide whether to update the list of approved traditional practices of slaughter to better consider animal rights.</p>
Value Non Controversial	<p>1. The government needs to decide whether to redesign the architecture of public schools under renovation to make them look more modern</p> <p>2. The government needs to decide whether to adjust the legal limits on building heights to make sure the city looks harmonious</p> <p>3. The government needs to decide whether to change quiet hours in cities to accommodate new residents.</p> <p>4. The government needs to decide whether to redesign public bathrooms in train stations to make them more welcoming</p> <p>5. The government needs to decide whether to redesign the signs for subway stations to make them compelling</p> <p>6. The government needs to decide whether to change the color of driving licenses to match those from other countries</p>

- Other Scales: Populist beliefs

To measure participants' endorsement of populist beliefs we used Uysal et al.'s (2024) measure where participants are presented with the statements shown below and asked to rate their level of agreement with each one of them using a 5-point scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

1. Politicians talk too much and do too little
2. An ordinary citizen would represent my interests better than a professional politician
3. What they call compromise in politics is in reality just a betrayal of principles
4. The people and not politicians should make the important political decisions
5. Politicians only care about the interests of the rich and powerful

- Other Scales: Psychological Distance to Science

As a validated predictor of science skepticism, we used the Psychological Distance to Science scale (PSYDISC) by Većkalov et al. (2024) which reflects, in four dimensions, the extent to which individuals perceive science as a tangible undertaking conducted by people similar to oneself (social), with effects in the here (spatial) and now (temporal), and as useful and applicable in the real world (hypothetical distance). Responses were given on a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Items marked with R were reverse-coded.

Temporal distance

1. Most of today's science is concerned with solving problems of the distant future.
2. Science is mainly focused on the distant future.
3. Scientists spend most of their time working on issues of the distant future.
4. We will see the impact of science more in the distant future than we do in the present.

Social distance

1. The prospect of working as a scientist seems beyond my reach.
2. I rarely interact with scientists in real life.
3. Scientists are very different from me.
4. It would be difficult for me to meet with a scientist.

Hypothetical distance

1. Scientific knowledge is a reliable way to solve important issues. R
2. Science provides accurate information about the world we live in. R
3. We can rely on science to deliver results that can be implemented in real life. R
4. I can see the effects of science, whether positive or negative, on the world. R

Spatial distance

1. Science and scientific research play a big role in my local area. R
2. Scientific research really contributes to my local area. R
3. People from my local area don't become scientists.
4. Very few scientists live or work in my town.

- Demographics

In our survey we asked age, gender (male/female/non-binary/prefer not to say/other: ____), and education (No schooling completed - Doctorate degree, Prefer not to say, other: ____).

To measure scientific education background, those who chose anything beyond high school were asked what was the main focus of their studies after high-school and had to choose from: Formal Sciences (for example Logic, Mathematics, etc); Natural Sciences (for example Biology, Chemistry, etc); Social sciences and Humanities (for example Politics, Economics, Sociology, etc); Arts and Architecture; Interdisciplinary (a combination of the above, describe below): ____; Other: ____; Prefer not to say.

To measure political ideology, orientation, and level of religiosity, we used the same measures as used in (Cologna et al., 2024). Political orientation was indicated on a 5-point Likert scale: Very left, left, center, right, very right / Prefer not to say. Political ideology as well: Very liberal, liberal, moderate, conservative, very conservative / Prefer not to say. Level of religiosity: How religious or spiritual are you? 5-point scale from ‘not at all’ to ‘extremely’/Prefer not to say.

- Attention checks
 - Stand-alone question: "click the option that is not a fruit" (multiple choice - apple, hamburger, peach, watermelon)
 - Within the main task: As another government decision statement, participants are told that to show that they are paying attention, they need to set their answer to Scientific Evidence/Opinion Polls only. There will be a second one with the reverse request.
 - Within the other scales: One of the statements they had to rate said “To show that you are paying attention, select ‘Strongly agree’ (for one of the scales) / ‘Strongly disagree’ (for the other scale)”.

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